

Fig. 1. Electrocapillary curves of Tl^{I} in the presence of (a) LPC: (1) 0.0, (2) 5.0×10^{-7} , (3) 1.0×10^{-6} , (4) 3.0×10^{-6} , (5) 7.0×10^{-6} and (6) 9.0×10^{-6} M; (b) SLS: (1) 0.0, (2) 5.0×10^{-7} , (3) 1.0×10^{-6} , (4) 3.0×10^{-6} , (5) 6.0×10^{-6} and (6) 8.0×10^{-6} M; (c) LPC+SLS: (1) 0.0, (2) $4.0 \times 10^{-7} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$, (3) $6.0 \times 10^{-7} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$, (4) $1.0 \times 10^{-6} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$, (5) $2.0 \times 10^{-6} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$ and (6) $3.0 \times 10^{-6} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$ M.

The values of $d\gamma/dC$ have been obtained from γ vs C plots.

The additive and antagonistic effects of mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants have been ascertained by determining their M.S.P. values, separately and in their mixtures. A comparison of the M.S.P. values in the two cases provides information as to the antagonistic or additive effects of mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants in the suppression of positive maximum of Tl^{I} . The M.S.P. values in respect of various surfactants and their mixtures have been determined and listed in Table 1. A perusal of this Table shows that the M.S.P. values in respect of the mixtures, LPC+SLS, LPC+Manoxol-OT, LPC+Tergitol-7, LPC+DBS, CPC+SLS, CPC+Tergitol-7, CPB+SLS, CPB+Tergitol-7, CTAB+SLS, CTAB+Tergitol-7, CDBAC+SLS and CDBAC+Tergitol-7, are smaller than those for individual surfactants, thereby indicating additive effects of these mixtures in the suppression of positive maximum of Tl^{I} . This is further supported by the fact that the values of ΓRT at the stage of just suppression of the maximum are larger for the above mentioned mixtures than those for the individual surfactants. However, in the case of the mixtures, CPC+Manoxol-OT, CPC+DBS, CPB+Manoxol-OT, CPB+DBS, CTAB+Manoxol-OT, CTAB+DBS, CDBAC+Manoxol-OT and CDBAC+DBS, the M.S.P. values are higher than those for the individual surfactants, thereby showing the antagonistic effects in the suppression of the maximum of Tl^{I} . This is supported by the smaller values of ΓRT at the stage of just suppression of the maximum.

Acknowledgement

The award of a Senior Research Fellowship by C.S.I.R., New Delhi, to one of the authors (I.B.) is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. S. LAL and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 898.
2. S. LAL and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 332.
3. G. RAM, Ph. D. Thesis, Agra University, 1978.
4. P. ZUMAN and I. M. KOLTHOFF, "Progress in Polarography", Interscience, New York, 1962, Vol. I, p. 88.
5. J. HEYROVSKY and J. KUTA, "Principles of Polarography", Academic, New York, 1966, p. 437.
6. E. L. COLICHMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4036.
7. J. HEYROVSKY, "A Polarographic Study of the Electrokinetic Phenomena of Adsorption, Electroreduction and Overpotential displayed at the Dropping Mercury Cathode", *Actualites Scientifiques et industrielles*, Paris, 1934, No. 90.
8. J. HEYROVSKY, in "Die Physikalischen Methoden der Chemischen Analyse", ed. W. BORRGER, Leipzig, 1936, Vol. 2, pp. 266-282.

Occurrence of 7,8-Epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain in *Didymocarpus podocarpa*

A. K. DAS*

North Bengal Campus, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Coochbehar-736 101

and

ANJAN BHATTACHARYYA and S. R. MITRA

Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 28 June 1982, revised 14 April 1986, accepted 2 August 1986

CHEMICAL investigation on two *Didymocarpus* species *D. pedicellata* and *D. aurentiaca* led to the isolation of a number of chalcones¹⁻⁴, quinochalcones⁵, flavanones^{6,7}, terpenoids⁸, and α -pyrones⁹.

* Present address: Department of Agricultural Chemistry & Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235.

Recently, three kaurenoid diterpenes were isolated from another *Didymocarpus* sp., *D. oblonga*¹⁰. In continuation of our work on *Didymocarpus* species, we became interested to examine yet another uninvestigated species *D. podocarpa*, growing in the Darjeeling area in West Bengal.

Extraction of the whole plant of *D. podocarpa* with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) led to the isolation of a compound which has been established as 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain (1) previously isolated from *D. aurentiaca*⁹.

(1)

Compound 1, m.p. 125–26°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} \pm 0^\circ$; R, 0.6 (CHCl₃—MeOH, 9.5 : 0.5) and 0.4 (CHCl₃), was crystallised as colourless needles (petroleum ether—benzene) and analysed for C₁₄H₁₂O₄ (*M*⁺ 244). It gave yellow colour with 5% alcoholic KOH solution which disappeared readily on acidification. It did not give any colour with FeCl₃. The ir spectrum (CHCl₃) of compound 1 revealed $\nu_{\max}$ 1710, 1626 (α, β -unsaturated six-membered lactone), 820 (an epoxide function), 760 and 740 cm⁻¹ (a monosubstituted benzene ring); and its nmr spectrum (60 MHz) δ 3.83 (3H, 5-OCH₃), 7.33 (5H, s, monosubstituted benzene ring), 6.11 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, proton of a 2-pyrone ring), 5.5 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, proton of a 2-pyrone ring), 4.36 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, methine protons of an epoxide group), 3.83 (1H, d, *J* 2Hz, methine proton of an epoxide group) showed resemblances with those of 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain. The mass spectrum of compound 1 *m/e* 244 (*M*⁺), 216 (*M*⁺—CO), 187 (*m/e* 216—CHO), 138 (C₇H₇O₃—H), 125 (*m/e* 244—C₈H₇O) and 77 (C₆H₅), was in accord with 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain. Finally, the identification of compound 1 was established by direct comparison with an authentic sample of 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain (m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra).

The occurrence of 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain in *D. aurentiaca* and *D. podocarpa* is of chemotaxonomic interest.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. M. Devys, I.C.S.N., C.N.R.S., Gif-sur-yvette, France, for spectral data, and also to Prof. N. Adityachaudhury, B.C.K.V., Kalyani, for providing authentic sample of 7,8-epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain.

References

1. S. O. AGARWAL, A. BHASKAR and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 9, and references cited therein.
2. A. BHASKAR and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 404, and references cited therein.

3. P. O. BOSE and N. ADITYACHAUDHURY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 55, 1198.
4. N. ADITYACHAUDHURY and P. DASKANUNGO, *Plant Biochem. J.*, 1976, 2, 65, and references cited therein.
5. K. O. SALOOJA, V. SHARMA and S. SIDDIQUI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1947, 68, 57.
6. P. O. BOSE and N. ADITYACHAUDHURY, *Phytochemistry*, 1978, 17, 587, and references cited therein.
7. A. BHATTACHARYYA, A. CHOWDHURY and N. ADITYACHAUDHURY, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1979, 348.
8. S. WARSII and S. SIDDIQUI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 14, 223.
9. N. ADITYACHAUDHURY, A. K. DAS and P. DASKANUNGO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1967, 14, 909.
10. S. R. MITRA, A. K. DAS, O. L. KIRTANIYA, N. ADITYACHAUDHURY, A. PATRA and A. K. MITRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 79, and references cited therein.

Flavonoid Glycosides from the Leaves of *Taxodium mucronatum*

M. KHABIR, (Miss) FEHMEEDA KHATOON

and

W. H. ANSARI*

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 31 July 1985, revised 7 April 1986,
accepted 2 August 1986

IN the absence of any record of work on monoflavonoids and their glycosides of *Taxodium mucronatum*, we studied these flavonoids of its leaves, and the isolation and characterisation of kaempferol, quercetin, quercetin-3-*O*- β -D-glucoside and quercetin-3-*O*- β -D-galactoside are presented here. The occurrence of two glycosides with the same aglycone unit in a plant is found rare in nature.

The air-dried leaves of *Taxodium mucronatum* (1 kg) collected from F.R.I., Dehra Dun (U.P.), were successively extracted with petroleum ether, benzene and acetone. The dried acetone extract was treated with hot water. The insoluble portion on column chromatography over silica gel yielded kaempferol and quercetin¹. The water soluble portion was extracted with butanol and the brown residue obtained after concentration was separated by column chromatography followed by preparative paper chromatography into two fractions A and B.

Compound-A: It was crystallised as yellow needle shaped clusters, m.p. 234–36°; gave green colour with FeCl₃; orange-red Shinoda test and a positive Molish test; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 255 and 368 nm, indicating the compound to be a flavonol glycoside. The pmr spectrum of its acetate showed it to be a monoglycoside. On acid hydrolysis it gave quercetin. The sugar was identified as glucose. Permethylation of the glucoside was carried out by Kuhn's method², which on hydrolysis gave quercetin 5,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ether, m.p. 194–96°. With AlCl₃ it showed a bathochromic shift of 62 nm in the long wavelength band, indicating that the